

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TECHNOLOGY AND FEATURES OF OBTAINING IMPRESSIONS DURING IMPLANTATION USING THE ALL-ON4 METHOD

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Abstract

A temporary prosthesis for the period of implant healing, which is 3-4 months, performs an aesthetic function and stabilizes the implants by connecting them. Otherwise, the recommendations for the rehabilitation period are the same as for any other implantation. Following a gentle diet is mandatory for every patient after surgery. The course of the rehabilitation period largely depends on the patient and on compliance with all the doctor's recommendations. To summarize, we can say that the All-on-4 technique is indicated in situations where it is not possible to install distant (distal) implants and at the same time we do not want (or cannot) perform complex bone grafting over the inferior alveolar nerves (on the lower jaw) or under the maxillary sinuses (on the upper jaw): in this case, All-on-4 implantation allows you to bypass these anatomically important formations.

Keywords: open and closed tray, All-on4 concept, virtual impressions.

Obtaining a high-quality impression from an implant of any type is a responsible task and an important condition for obtaining an accurate and precision design. Thus, the occurrence and development of stress on the implant is excluded. Different techniques for taking classical impressions from implants differ in accuracy. The result will depend on several factors, such as the placement of the implants at different angles (for example, in the All-on-4 concept), the splinting of the impression copings, the use of a closed or open tray, and the level of the implant platform. In 1998, Dr. Paulo Malo successfully treated the first patient using the All-on-4 concept. Since then, hundreds of thousands of patients have been treated with this concept. The situation is complicated by the fact that with the All-on-4 concept, the distal implants are located at a large angle relative to the horizontal and frontal planes, and the anterior implants are most often located parallel to each other; thus, when taking an impression, there is less chance of deviation in accuracy in that area. The purpose of the study is to systematize the main problematic factors of the classical technique of taking impressions with the All-on-4 concept, which occur and affect the accuracy of the orthopedic design.

Material and methods.

In August 2018, an electronic search was conducted in the dental libraries Pubmed and Medline using the keywords: impressions, precision, all-on-4, angulated implants. The search included articles without taking into account the year of publication. All studies described in the articles were done in vitro. A review of 35 articles was conducted, of which all conclusions were divided into 6 groups: 1. Comparison of impression accuracy when using an open and closed tray. 2.

Impression material. 3. Splinted and non-splinted impression copings. 4. Angulation of implants. 5. Depth of implant placement. 6. Passive fit and adherence of the prosthetic structure. Results. 1. Comparison of impression accuracy when using an open and closed tray. From a review of 19 articles, 10 described that tray type had no effect on cast accuracy; 7 describe that impressions taken with an open tray are more accurate, and 2 articles indicate the advantage of a closed tray. 2. Impression material. The materials discussed and compared in the articles are hydrocolloids, impression plaster, polyesters, polyvinylsiloxanes and polysulfides in various consistencies and combinations. Polyester masses are recommended for use in 7 articles. One article also stated that there is no significant difference in impressions made with polyesters and polyvinylsiloxanes. Another article describes that polyesters are preferred for total work, such as All-on-4, or when taking impressions of multiple implants. As an advantage, the authors point to their high dimensional stability and Shore hardness. For partially edentulous patients, they are not recommended due to the difficulty of removing the impression from the oral cavity. In such cases, the authors recommend A-silicones. A-silicones are recommended in two articles. Polysulfides are in only one article. 3. Splinted and non-splinted impression copings. There is no consensus on this issue in the literature review. Of the 16 articles analyzed, the group of authors in 6 of them claim that the results are the same for both methods and there is no significant difference between them. Another group of authors advise the use of splinting, and this is described in 8 articles. A third group of authors describe that more accurate impressions are obtained when impression copings are not splinted. 4. Angulation of implants. From an analysis of 8 articles that

examined the relationship between the degree of angulation of implants (10/90 degrees of inclination) and the quality of the resulting impressions, 3 of them confirmed that the more the degree of angulation increases, the more the impression exhibits inaccuracy[1]. In two articles, the authors do not note the influence of the degree of angulation on the accuracy of the impression. However, comparison based on this criterion is difficult, since different articles present different combinations of research methods [2,3]. 5. Depth of implant placement. Only one article describes the study of this parameter. The results show that for impressions made of polyvinylsiloxane material, the depth of the implants does not matter. For polyesters, this is already being explored by various methods for preparing a working model, as well as design preparation technologies, including CAD/CAM. Another article confirms that a 100% passive fit cannot be achieved and therefore the need to divide large structures is important, and impressions made from this material with deeply placed implants are more inaccurate[4]. 6. Passive fit and adherence of the prosthetic structure. Lots of authors and then solder them together.

Conclusion.

Open tray impressions with coupled copings performed better, but based on the results of this study, neither method should be preferred based on accuracy. For highly angulated implants, an open tray is preferred. Today, both polyesters and polyvinylsiloxanes make it possible to obtain decent quality prints, but there is no 100% accuracy. The process of making a plaster model can lead to distortions associated with volumetric shrinkage of materials. The greater the degree of angulation of the implant, the less accurate the

impression will be. The deeper the implant is located, the less part of the impression coping remains outside, therefore, the coping will be held less firmly in the impression material. Our opinion is that traditional impression techniques with the All-on-4 concept are very dependent on the experience and skill of the orthopedic clinical specialist. Today, virtual impressions provide high accuracy and make the results of orthopedic treatment more predictable. Therefore, we can safely say that the future belongs to digital technologies.

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